

**A STUDY ON ACADEMIC STRESS AMONG HIGHER
SECONDARY STUDENTS: AN EMPIRICAL
APPROACH**

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Abstract

Stress is a normal phenomenon in everyone's life. It is a state of an individual under exhausting circumstances in different areas of life, i.e. family, school, health, business organization etc. Students especially of higher secondary classes have to undergo the experiences of stress due to the pressure of studies, expectations of parents, teachers, and self, peer pressure, career demands resulting a lot of burden on delicate minds. Therefore, it is necessary to understand the causes of academic stress among higher secondary students; to point out their resources to combat it and thereby enhance their well being. Stress and its manifestations, such as anxiety, depression, and burnout, have always were as a common problem among people in different professions and occupations. In the last few decades, alarm has already been provoked by the proliferation of books, research reports, popular articles and the growing number of organized workshops, aiming to teach people how to cope with this phenomenon. The present study consists of 250 eleven standard students studying in higher secondary schools situated in Aligarh District of Uttar Pradesh, India. The sample was selected by using simple random sampling technique. The present study reveals that the higher secondary students are having moderate level of academic stress. The male student's academic stress is higher than female students. The urban student's academic stress is higher than rural students. The Government school student's academic stress is less than private school student. The science subject student's academic stress is higher than arts student. The findings of this study could be useful for students to know their level of stress and they can take up necessary and sufficient practices so as to reduce their academic stress.

Keywords: *Stress, Academic Stress, Management of Stress, Higher Secondary School Students.*

Introduction

Stress is viewed as a negative emotional, cognitive, behavioral and physiological process that occurs as a person tries to adjust to or deal with stressors (Bernstein et al, 2008). The effect of stress is understood in many walks of life with diverse population especially among students. Richlin-Klonsky (2003) reported that "stress has lessened academic performance, hinder with a student's capability to involve in and add to campus life, and raise the probability of substance abuse and other potentially destructive behaviours". Stressors are defined as circumstances that disrupt, or threaten to disrupt, individuals' daily functioning and cause people to make adjustments (Auerbach & Gambling, 1998). Auerbach and Gambling (1998) regard stress as an unpleasant state of emotional and physiological arousal that individuals experience in situations that they perceive as dangerous or threatening to their well-being. However, stress is perceived in different ways and may mean different things to different individuals. Stress is perceived as events or situations that cause individual to feel tension, pressure, or negative emotions including anxiety and anger. It is important to note that stress can have both positive and negative effects on people. It means that stress may be a normal, adaptive reaction to threat. Its role is to signal and prepare individuals to take defensive action. Take for instance, fear of things that present realistic threats motivates individuals to deal with them or avoid them. Most psychologists assert that moderate stress motivates individual to achieve and fuels creativity, although stress may hinder individuals from performance or difficult tasks. Stress can be imposed on an individual by unusual physical condition such as excessive heat or cold, illness, deprivation of oxygen, or exposure to strong light. Standing at attention for a long time, climbing a mountain, or continuous immersion in water can also place strong demands for adaptation on the individual.

Sources of Stress

Bernstein et al. (2008) define the sources of stress as every circumstance or event that threatens to disrupt people's daily

functioning and causes them to make adjustments. these sources of stress are called "Stressors". Stressor are demands made by the internal or external environment that upset balance, thus affecting physical and psychological well-being and requiring action to restore balance (Lazarus & Cohen, 1977). However, they differ from the degree of severity and duration of stress; what is stressful for an individual may not be a stressor for another.

For example, missing some lectures may be stressful for the first year undergraduates students, but may not be stressful for another student depending on his or her degree of expectations. Taking his final exam or sitting in rush hour traffic is not equivalent to being attacked by an angry Lion, where high arousal could facilitate fighting or feeling. Catastrophic events, major life-changes, and daily hassles are regarded as major categories of stressors that create demands to which people must adjust. Major life changes (e.g. losing a job, divorce, illness, death of a spouse or family member, and imprisonment) can be regarded as stressful situations for every adult. Most stress people experience in their everyday lives is caused by daily hassles. Daily hassles can also be viewed as the irritations, pressures, and annoyance that might not be significant stressors by themselves but whose cumulative effects can be significant. This can be related to individuals' jobs, every day living circumstances and personal relationships (Bernstein et al. (2008).

Effects of Stress

It has been argued that an individual can have possibly anxious thoughts, difficulty to concentrate or remember because of being stressed. Stress can lead to change in people's behaviours, such as nail biting, heavy breathing, teeth clinging and hand wringing. When people are stressed, they may feel cold hands and feet, butterflies in stomach, and sometimes--increased heart rate, which all are regarded as common physiological effects of stress, which can be connected to emotion of anxiety (Auerbach & Gramling, 1998). Physical and psychological responses to stress generally occur together, principally when stressors become more intense.

However, one category of stress responses can influence other responses. For instance, mild chest pain may lead to the psychological stress responses of worrying about getting a heart attack. Physical responses can be when a person escapes from a terrible accident or some other frightening events, he or she experience rapid breathing, increased heart beating, sweating and even shaking little later. These reactions are part of a general pattern known as the fight-or-flight syndrome.

Coping With Stress

Stress does not affect all people equally, but stress can lead to illness and negative experiences. Coping with stress is therefore an important factor. It affects whether and how people search for medical care and social support and how they believe the advice of the professionals (Passer and Smith, 2007). One model that is useful in understanding stress among students is Person Environment Model (PEM |). According to one variation of this model, stressful events can be appraised by an individual as "challenging or "threatening (Lazarus, 1996). When students appraise their education is seen as a threat, however, stress can elicit feelings of helpless and a foreboding sense of loss.

Academic Stress

Academic stress is mental distress with respect to some anticipated frustration associated with academic failure or even unawareness to the possibility of such failure. Students have to face academic demands, for example, school examination, answering questions in the class, showing progress in school subjects. Understanding what the teacher is teaching, competing with other class mates, fulfilling teachers and parents academic expectations. These demand may tax or exceed available resources of the students. As a consequence, they can be under stress, since the demand is related to achievement of an academic goal. So, academic is related to the achievement of an academic goal.

Stress and its manifestations such as anxiety, depression, and burnout, have always been seen as a common problem among

people in different professions and occupations. In the last few decades, alarm has already been provoked by the proliferation of books, research reports, popular articles and the growing number of organized workshops, aiming to teach people how to cope with this phenomenon (Keinan & Perlberg, 1986). Academic stress among students have long been researched on, and researchers have identified stressors as too many assignments, competitions with other students, failures and poor relationships with other students or lecturers (Fairbrother & Warn, 2003). Academic stressors include the student's perception of the extensive knowledge base required and the perception of an inadequate time to develop it (Carveth et al, 1996). Student report experiencing academic stress at predictable times each semester with the greatest source of academic stress resulting from taking and studying for examinations, grade competition, and the large amount of content to master in a small amount of time (Abouserie, 1994). When stress is perceived negatively or becomes excessive, students experience physical and psychological impairment. Methods to reduce stress by students often include effective time management, social support, positive reappraisal, and engagement in leisure pursuits (Murphy & Archer, 1996). The pressure to perform well in the examination or test and time allocated makes academic environment very stressful (Erkutlu & Chafra, 2006). This is likely to affect the social relations both within the institution and outside which affects the individual person's life in terms of commitment to achieving the goals (Fairbrother & Warn, 2003).

Bisht (1989) has defined academic stress as a demand related to academics that tax or exceed the available resources (internal or external) as cognitively appeared by the stunned involved. According to Bisht, academic stress reflects perception of individual's academic frustrations, academic conflict, academic pressure and academic anxiety. Academic stress is an important factor accounting for variation in academic achievement. It also contributes to major mental health hazards, problems both physical and mental stress related dismiss. Stress makes a significant

contribution to the prediction of subsequent school performance and act as a negative predictor of academic performance in school children. Ender et al, 1994 shows the components of Academic stress. High school students cite day to day stresses of school (eg. tests, grades, home work, academic and achievement expectations) among their greatest stressors (Crystal et al, 1994; de Anda et al. 2000; Ohman and Jarvis, 2000).

Causes of Academic Stress on Students

Academic pressure is a significant source of stress for higher secondary school students (Hashim, 2003; Olpin, 1997; Tyrrell, 1992). Identified sources of academic related stress have included fear of falling behind with coursework, finding the motivation of study, time pressures, financial worries, and concerns about academic ability (Tyrell, 1992). Additionally, students report stress over struggling to meet academic standards, time management worries, and concerns over grades (Olpin, 1997). Additionally these sources may exist easily throughout the life span of college students' academic careers and may result in school students' experiencing a great deal of stress during their school career. If prevention efforts are to be developed to assist students in dealing with and avoiding academic related stress, a greater understanding of the relationship among student's use of coping strategies, social support, experiences of being parented, and academic related stress needs to be gained. Causes of stress on students include both positive and negative stress, but focus will be on the negative causes of stress of students.

Academics: Probably first among the causes of stress on students is academic pressure. Simply tackling more difficult assignments can demand stress management techniques. it might be wise for teachers to introduce students to this stress with an assignment such as a "Causes of Stress on Students Essay". Requiring students to interview older students and educators, as well as research the Internet on the subject, could help them prepare for the stresses of academic challenges.

Environment: The school environment itself can be a cause of stress on students. Students moving into secondary education find it challenging to constantly move around to classes. Those matriculating to tertiary education are challenged with leaving home and establishing a new life in a new setting. Both can cause stress on students.

Extra Co-curricular: Colleges pressure high school students to engage in extracurricular activities such as choirs, clubs, sports, band or volunteer work. The presence of these on a student application can go far towards acceptance. Hence in college, extracurricular activities still cause stress on students, once their presence on a job application is also an asset.

Peers: Like dating, peer relationships can provide estruses or distress. As peers apply pressure in regard to dress behaviour, choice of friends or sex, and many other areas of life, that pressure can become a huge presence of stress on students.

Parental Pressure: Finally, students at either level experience stress from parental pressures. Parents want their children to succeed in school. They want to see good grades, but they also want to see success in life's other areas. In their attempts to guide their children, parents can become one of the major causes of stress on students. It is wise for parents and others who work with students to take time to recognize the stresses students face. If they then provide stress management techniques, they will do much to relieve and encourage their students.

Review of Related Studies

Shibnath Deb, Eshen Strodl and Jiandong Sun (2012): Academic related stress among private secondary school students in India. The purpose of this study is to examine the prevalence of academic stress and exam anxiety among private secondary school students in India as well as the associations with socio-economic and study-related factors. Participants were 400 adolescent students (52 percent male)

from five private secondary schools in Kolkata who were studying in grades 10 and 12. Findings revealed that 35 and 37 percent reported high or very high of academic stress and exam anxiety respectively. All students reported high levels of academic stress, but those who had lower grades reported higher levels of stress than those with higher grades.

Need and Significance of the Study

In today's highly competitive world, students face various academic problems including exam stress, disinterest in attending classes and inability to understand the subject. Academic stress is the feeling of anxiety or apprehension over one's performance in the academic activities. It can lead to students being unable to perform to the best of their abilities in examinations. At school there is a range of academic pressure felt, derived from a need for perfection, worry over grades, parental pressure, competition, sports, or a tough class load. The nervous breakdowns, panic attacks, burnouts, and depression are also apparent in many younger students. The same situation is not always stressful for all people, and all people do not undergo the same feelings or off-putting thoughts when stressed. Students were considered to be the future pillars who take the responsibilities to take our country to the next phase they should be in a better way. To know this, the investigator decided to analyze the academic stress among higher secondary students.

Statement of the Problem

The problem undertaken by the investigator is stated as, **A Study on Academic Stress among Higher Secondary Students: An Empirical Approach.**

Objectives of The Study

The investigator of the present study framed the following objectives:

1. To find out the level of academic stress among high secondary students in Aligarh district,

Uttar Pradesh, India.

2. To find out whether there is significant difference between the following sub samples with respect to academic stress:
 - (i) Gender (Male/Female)
 - (ii) Streams of Study (Science/ Arts)
 - (iii) Type of Family (Nuclear family /Joint Family)
 - (iv) Management (Government/Private)
 - (v) Family Income

Hypotheses of The Study

The investigator of the present study framed the following hypotheses:

1. There is no significant difference in the academic stress of the higher secondary school students with respect to their Gender.
2. There is no significant difference in the academic stress of the higher secondary school students with respect to their streams of study.
3. There is no significant difference in the academic stress of the higher secondary school students with respect to their Type of Family.
4. There is no significant difference in the academic stress of the higher secondary school students with respect to their Type of School Management.
5. There is no significant mean difference in the academic stress of the higher secondary school students with respect to their Family Income.

The Method

In the present study, the investigator applied survey type of method. The normative group method studies, describes and interprets what exists at present.

Sample

The present study consists of 250 eleven standard students studying in higher secondary schools located in Aligarh district of Uttar Pradesh, India. The sample was selected by using simple random

sampling technique. The sample form a representative sample of the entire population.

Tool Used

The investigator of the present study selected and used the academic stress scale which was constructed and developed by A.O. Busari (20110. It has five-point Likert scale with 40 statements.

Description of Academic Stress Scale

One of the important objectives of the present investigation is to find out the level of academic stress among higher secondary school students. For this purpose the investigator used the Academic Stress Scale constructed dnad standardized by A.O. Busari. This scale consists of as many as 40 items an each item has five alternative responses i.e. "No Stress", "Slightly Stress", "Moderate Stress", "Highly Stress" and "Extremely High Stress".

So the scoring to the response given by the students should be like the following:

Response	Weightage
No Stress	0
Slightly Stress	1
Moderate Stress	2
Highly Stress	3
Extremely High Stress	4

High scores are an indication of high stress and low scores are an indication of low stress.

Statistical Techniques Used

For the analysis of the data, the following statistics techniques have been used:

- (i) Descriptive analysis (Mean & S.D.) and
- (ii) Differential analysis ('t' test).

Analysis and Interpretation of the Data

The data is analyzed using SPSS package. the collected data were subjected to statically analysis. The mean and standard deviation for the variable academic stress scores were computed for the entire sample.

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis-1: There is no significant difference in the academic stress of the higher secondary school students with respect to their Gender.

Table 1: Showing the Mean, S.D. and 't'-Value of higher secondary school students academic stress with regard to Gender

S.No.	Gender	N	Mean	SD	't'-value	Level of Significance	Remarks
1.	Male	118	152.85	42.04	4.0333	< 0.01	S
2.	Female	132	132.41	38.09			

It is inferred from the above table 1 that there is significant difference in the academic stress of the higher secondary school students with regard to their Gender.

Hypothesis-2: There is no significant difference in the academic stress of the higher secondary school students with respect to their Stream of Study.

Table 2: Showing the Mean, S.D. and 't'-Value of higher secondary school students academic stress with regard to their Stream of Study

S.No.	Streams of Study	N	Mean	SD	't'-value	Level of Significance	Remarks
1.	Arts	129	141.18	49.27	0.4793	> 0.05	NS
2.	Science	121	144.15	48.65			

It is inferred from the above table 2 that there is no significant difference in the academic stress of the higher secondary school

students with regard to their Stream of Study.

Hypothesis-3: There is no significant difference in the academic stress of the higher secondary school students with respect to their type of family.

Table 3: Showing the Mean, S.D. and 't'-Value of higher secondary school students academic stress with regard to their Type of Family

S.No.	Type of Family	N	Mean	SD	't'- value	Level of Significance	Remarks
1.	Nuclear	163	137.25	52.66	2.3969	< 0.05	S
2.	Joint	87	152.67	39.27			

It is inferred from the above table 3 that there is significant difference in the academic stress of the higher secondary school students with regard to their Type of Family.

Hypothesis-4: There is no significant difference in the academic stress of the higher secondary school students with regard to their Type of School Management.

Table 4: Showing the Mean, S.D. and 't'-Value of higher secondary school students academic stress with regard to their Type of School Management

S.No.	Type of School	N	Mean	SD	't'-value	Level of Significance	Remarks
1.	Government	127	151.6	42.04	2.1294	< 0.05	S
2.	Private	123	162.8	41.09			

It is inferred from the above table 4 that there is significant difference in the academic stress of the higher secondary school students with regard to their Type of School Management.

Hypothesis-5: There is no significant difference in the academic stress of the higher secondary school students with regard to their

Family Income.

Table 5: Showing the Mean, S.D. and 't'-Value of higher secondary school students academic stress with regard to their Family Income

S.No.	Sources of Variance	Sum of squares	df	Mean of squares	'F' ratio	Level of Significance	Remarks
1.	Between Groups	1242.5742	2	621.2871	0.2583	> 0.05	NS
2.	Within Groups	594029.5875	247	2404.9781			
	Total	595272.1617	249				

It is inferred from the above table 5 that there is significant difference in the academic stress of the higher secondary school students with regard to their Family Income.

Major Findings of the Study

The major findings of the study are as following:

1. There is significant difference in the academic stress of the higher secondary school students with regard to their Gender.
2. There is no significant difference in the academic stress of the higher secondary school students with regard to their Stream of Study
3. There is significant difference in the academic stress of the higher secondary school students with regard to their Type of Family.
4. There is significant difference in the academic stress of the higher secondary school students with regard to their Type of School Management.
5. There is significant difference in the academic stress of the higher secondary school students with regard to their Family Income.

Suggestions for Further Research

- (i) The present study has focused only on the higher secondary students. Similar studies would be conducted with high school students as well as college students.
- (ii) The method of teaching plays an important role in academic stress, as the teaching method would reduce academic stress. The family and school environment would also be studied.

Educational Implications

Academic stress of students is found to be a considerable factor with regard to academic achievement. The overall academic stress consists of learning difficulties, attitude towards school, time management, exam stress, peer group relation. The school should arrange the necessary environmental conditions to reduce the student's academic stress. The teachers should concentrate in reducing the academic stress by grabbing the individual attention of the students while handling the respective classes. The education given in the classroom should reflect the application of life skills which enables them to face this highly competitive world. It should not be conducted only in the view point of examination.

Conclusion

The present study reveals that boys have less academic stress than girls. The students belonging to private schools have high academic stress than the government schools. Stress can be positive or negative. Stress can be positive when the situation offers an opportunity for a person who faces social, physical, organizational and emotional problems. This is a great challenge for present generation learners in education. This positive response prepares the body for action and activates the higher thinking centers of the brain. Academic stress has a close association in the attainment of academic achievement. Therefore, every attempt should be made to create a stress free environment at the institutional level among the students of higher secondary schools.

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